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Introduction of an innovative method to the field of education in Uzbekistan

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Annotation: In this article, you will find examples of the methods and changes introduced by our great teachers in the performance of the instrument. You will get information about the high skills, experiences and innovations of major professional musicians and teachers.

Key words: instrument, innovation, style, music, interactive method.

Realizing the need to reform the educational system, in practice requires educational institutions to participate in innovative processes, to see the opportunity to create themselves in the existing innovative space and, most importantly, to reduce specific innovations.

This situation is very relevant today, because this process (innovative process) serves as a condition for the existence of educational institutions (both directly and figuratively), as well as a condition for social protection of future generations and relations of the team of pedagogues. Life presents educational institutions with new, seemingly impossible tasks, that is, working on the old ones, developing specific innovations and putting them into practice.

It is futile and dangerous to resist this process. We have no choice and are forced to participate in this fast-track process (chase process). The most important thing in this process is to participate intelligently and usefully for the development of our small community. Many experts believe that the ability to change is the decisive factor of development, the main factor that ensures the competitiveness of one or another educational institution.

Today, the traditional and public in the school and higher education system innovative processes are entering the development of educational institutions instead of the existing educational and training processes. Innovation (in-lik, novus-new) means innovation, novelty.

Innovative education usually means introducing new (useful) elements into the educational process. Therefore, innovation in the education system is directly related to change. Such changes of the educational system:

- purpose, content, method, technology, organization form and management system;
- originality in pedagogical activity and organization of learning process to do;
- to the system of control and assessment of educational levels;
- educational and methodical administration;
- system of educational affairs;
- curriculum and educational programs;
- depends on the activity of the student and the teacher.

The novelty is relativity in the historical aspect. The novelty has a clear historical character, that is, it can appear before a short time, it can become a norm or become obsolete in a short time. During the development of a school or higher education system, perhaps the education system as a whole:

- absolute novelty (similarity, absence of a prototype);
- relatively new;
- unique, inventive ones are taken into account.

News types (types) are grouped according to different bases in the school and higher education system:

The first classification (group) is based on the introduction of innovations and their relevance to the pedagogical process that occurs in the school and higher education system. Based on the understanding of this process, it is possible to distinguish the following types of innovation:

- the purpose and content of education;
- pedagogical process methodology, tasks, methods, technologies;
- forms and means of organizing education and training;
- management, pedagogue and student activities.

The second classification (group) into the educational system is based on the sign of the scale (volume) of the introduction of innovation. The following changes can be distinguished here:

- unrelated local and separate (one

- bilaterality);
- complex, interconnected;
- systemic, covering the entire school and higher education system.

The third classification (group) is based on innovative capabilities. In this case, it is taken into account:

- improvement of educational programs, curricula, structures,
- modification of the known and accepted related to inventiveness, changing appearances;

- introduction of innovations specific to combinatorics (changes);
- radical changes.

The fourth classification (group) of innovations is grouped based on their characteristics compared to the previous ones. In this approach, novelty is determined by those who exchange, cancel, or disclose. In this case, as a source of renewal in the school and higher education system:

- social as the need of the country, region, city, district order;
- the law of regional and regional significance of the social order and reflected in documents;
- achievement of complex human science, advanced pedagogical experience;
- the intuition of leaders and pedagogues in testing mistakes and shortcomings and creativity;
- experimental work;

The innovative policy that is developing in our country sets important and responsible tasks for education. The document on education for an innovative society in the 21st century, which was adopted by the Group of Eight in St. Petersburg in July 2006, calls for a solution to the problem and to take into account the goals of education.

In the future development strategy of science and innovation, creating an innovative person, that is, regardless of his work, he should be inclined to innovation and new knowledge. Therefore, modern innovation efficiency is emerging today.

On the website of current national projects, the phrase innovative education appears, and it says that innovative education requires teaching to be carried out in the process of creating new knowledge. This requires to distinguish between the concept of innovative educational technologies and new innovative educational concepts.

The field of education is one of the first in our country to start an active innovative movement. At a certain stage, at the end of the 20th century, such actions were left alone. For example, views on collective teaching of teaching by A.G. Rivin and V.K. Dyachenko, D.B. Elkonin, V.V. Davbidov, L.V. Zankov on developmental innovative education have gained some importance in a short time. At the same time, other innovative educational technologies: dialectical teaching methods (A.I. Goncharuk, V.L. Zarina), individual approach to teaching (A.A. Yarulov), ecology and dialectics (L.V. Tarasov), heuristic teaching (A.V. Khutorskoy), dialogue culture (V.S. Bibler, S.Yu.Kurganov), project-based reflection (G.P.Shedrovitskaya) and others.

✓ The above-mentioned technologies are aimed at increasing learning in education, increasing interest in the educational process, improving understanding of educational material, forming functional literacy, project literacy, theoretical thinking, ecological and economic thinking, communication, social activity, civic consciousness, awareness of the little and solving other tasks. was

✓ For the educational technologies listed above, the innovators were only pedagogues, their innovations were directed to the formation of necessary qualities in students, and attention was not paid to the orientation of innovative thinking and ability to innovative activities. The expressed opinions require a separate consideration of the concepts of innovative educational technologies and innovative education as follows:

- innovative learning technologies and programs are all learning technologies, is the result of pedagogical innovation activity of their creator and developer.

- innovative education is such innovative educational technologies and programs in which the pedagogue is the result of innovative activity and is the creator (generation) of the innovative ideas of the students;

- mono-innovativeness of production (experts innovation) corresponds to the fact that education is not mono-innovative - (pedagogical innovation), its innovativeness, pedagogical innovation, their consequence, is the innovation of those being educated.

In this case, the urgency of the issue is to develop existing mono-innovative educational technologies to bi-innovative state. These are confirmed by a few practical proofs in the case of a number of foreign teachers, in the case of experiments and inventions created by them. Based on the achievements of modern science, it has been

proven that the theory of solving problems can be solved by means of IMEN. In the scientific laboratories of a number of developed countries (IMEN) a new method called IMEN - inventing knowledge for pedagogy was created. The integration framework of IMEN was developed together with all the most common innovative pedagogical technologies.

The process of global changes in the world, changes in the economic and socio-cultural spheres of our country require serious attention to be paid to specialists being trained in the educational system. In the field of pedagogical education, we see that in the 1980s and 1990s, the system of personnel training, retraining and professional development acquired an innovative character as a single, integrated system, focusing on the following processes:

- the independence of education (decentralization) allowed the independent development of this field in certain regions and the formation of order portfolios for certain specialists;
- democratization of higher educational institutions, provided an opportunity to ensure independence in determining the form, means and conditions of organizing the pedagogical process;
- in accordance with the types of institutions of general education and music schools, it gave opportunities for the pedagogue to design his pedagogical activities and use the educational subject he teaches as a means of developing students, and to take into account the needs of general education and music schools in this regard;
- provides for the need to satisfy the personal interests of the student, designed to develop individual educational programs that include the possibility of choosing the content and level of the received pedagogical education;
- it allows to prepare professional trainers in a short period of time based on its different levels of capabilities.

Although the above-mentioned processes had a strong impact in certain periods, in this case, recognizing the existence of a certain dialectical relationship between the traditional and innovative processes of personnel training, it is necessary to pay attention to the unique aspects of each of the traditional and innovative training.

The content of traditional pedagogic education is focused on the preparation of specific educational subjects and specialized teachers. In the traditional system of professional-pedagogical training, the educational process is based on an active

approach, and the relations between the participants in this process are isolated in the form of subject-object. Here, the subject - the teacher - is in certain limited conditions, his activities are governed by the curriculum and curriculum, and relations are strictly defined. The object is limited to a certain level of knowledge of the student.

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In the traditional educational process, cross-functional imitation, imitation, working by example, homogeneity of social and interpersonal interaction, external control and evaluation of the result, all this does not allow the reduction of knowledge motives and the expansion of knowledge motives.

During 1990-2000, new approaches to pedagogical training were developed in theory and practice. Practical processes started from above and below. Action from above begins with the introduction of new curricula in higher education. According to the new educational plans, higher education had the opportunity to independently organize educational subjects by courses.

Such democratic freedom was accepted by the departments and faculties with some creativity, and this bottom-up change gave rise to many pedagogic-innovator movements. Several indicators of innovative actions, including organizational, meaningful, methodical indicators, were created and put into practice. These cases were discussed as the main issue of many pedagogy and psychology department meetings, and on the basis of the state curriculum and programs, each higher educational institution began to develop its own working curriculum and working educational programs.

This made it possible to introduce and maintain innovative technologies of each subject. These changes led to the increase of pedagogical-psychological subjects in the curricula of all higher education institutions in the republic by 20-25%.

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